

**SYARIAH COMPLIANCE ON HALAL FOOD BASED ON CERTAIN AYAT IN
SURAT AL-MA'IDAH**

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ABSTRACT

According to Quran, *Al-Halal* is anything that benefits and does not cause harm to the body, mind and religion, the Sunnah as well has confirmed the importance of seeking the *Halal* food since it is considered as requirement and prerequisite for the acceptance of righteous deeds. Therefore, the food in order to be *Halal*, has to be good. In some countries where there are many sects or the Muslim communities are minorities, the Muslims are cautious when it comes to consuming the manufactured or processed food by the foreign companies. As a result, these Muslims abstain from eating their food and be cautious of committing unlawful deeds. I have witnessed some Muslims who do not bother themselves in eating in such foreign food chains restaurants and do not question whether the food served is *Halal* or *Haram* (prohibited). Such behaviour does contradict with the sharia rules and regulations in clarifying the rules of *Halal*, This research aims to shed light on the most crucial Sharia rules and regulations related to the acquisition of *Halal* food based on certain Ayat in Surat Al-Ma'idah in order to raise awareness among Muslims regarding the provisions of foods that are permissible and forbidden in the light of contemporary developments. Furthermore, it allows the international and domestic food companies to have an idea about the sharia rules and regulations of food processing from production to marketing. The researcher will use the inductive method to trace the verses that indicate the provisions of *Halal*- foods in Surat Al-Ma'idah and its statement in the books of Tafsir and Fiqh, and then the deductive approach to conclude the most important Shari'ah restrictions related to the acquisition of Halal food. The authors has reached to ten important findings of Shari'a controls and have discussed them in the paper content.

Field of Research: Surat Al-Ma'idah, Shari'a Compliance, Necessity, Halal Food, Animals.

Introduction:

This topic has been taken up in eight Madani verses, and the meaning of the compliance in this research is: "A legitimate ruling which is practical and general, falls under it more than one question from one chapter" (Group of Authors: 2013), and the food is: "What is the growth of the body and its strength from the food, drink and milk" (Ibnu Manzor: 1993), and Halal is: "what is authorized by the religion to do it" (Qaradawi: 2012), and hence we can define the Shari'a Compliance on Halal Food as: "Sharia provisions regarding the issues of food and drinks which is authorized by the religion", then these legitimate controls that we are going to mention it in this research it includes the food and drinks, and from the most important Shari'a Compliance on Halal Food derived from this surah are as follows:

FIRST: THE IMPERMISSIBILITY OF FORBIDDING THE LAWFUL FOODS AND PERMITTING THE UNLAWFUL FOODS

Allah has mentioned in his book that it is not permissible to forbid what Allah has permitted to benefit from it such food and other good things, he says: (O Believers, do not make unlawful those pure things which Allah has made lawful for you, and do not go beyond the limit; indeed Allah does not like the transgressors) (al-Maa'idah 5: 87), and it was reported that the reason for the revelation of this verse is

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that the companions of the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) were deprived themselves from goodness and flesh, so Allah has revealed this to them according to Abu Ja'far al-Tabari (Al-Tabari: 2001), that's why Rashid Rida says: "The abstinence of a person from the good things that he had with the innate preacher to enjoy them is a sin that he earns on himself in this world, and he deserves the punishment of Allah in the Hereafter due to his innovation in the religion of Allah, and the consequent loss of some of Allah's rights and the rights of the worshipers of Allah Such as wasting the rights of his wife or children, and not to mention if he became an example to others, and he was a reason for the exaggeration of some people in religion and their prohibition on themselves and on those who follow them what Allah has permitted" (Rashid Reza: 1990), And in Sunan al-Tirmidhi from Awn ibn Abi Juhayfah, from his father, he said: The Prophet (saws) made a bond of brotherhood between Salman (May Allah be pleased with him) and Abu Ad-Darda (May Allah be pleased with him)⁷. Salman paid a visit to Abu Ad-Darda, and found Um Ad-Darda' (May Allah be pleased with her) dressed in shabby clothes and asked her why she was in that state. She replied, "Your brother Abu Ad-Darda is not interested in (the luxuries of) this world.", In the meantime Abu Ad-Darda came and prepared a meal for Salman. Salman requested Abu Ad-Darda to eat (with him), but Abu Ad-Darda said, "I am fasting" Salman said, "I am not going to eat unless you eat". So, Abu Ad-Darda ate (with Salman). When it was night and (a part of the night passed), Abu Ad-Darda got up (to offer the night prayer), but Salman told him to sleep and Abu Ad-Darda slept. After sometime Abu Ad-Darda again got up but Salman told him to sleep. When it was the last hours of the night, Salman told him to get up then, and both of them offered the prayer. Salman told Abu Ad-Darda, "Your Lord has a right on you, your soul has a right on you, and your family has a right on you; so you should give the rights of all those who has a right on you". Abu Ad-Darda came to the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) and narrated the whole story. The Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) said, "Salman has spoken the truth" Tirmidhi: 1975).

Also Allah has mentioned in Surat Al-Maida that it is not permissible to invalidate forbidden foods and other sins, such as Allah forbids hunting while on Pilgrimage (Hajj or Umrah), he says: (O you who believe! Kill not the game while you are in a state of Ihraam [for Hajj or 'Umrah (pilgrimage)]) (al-Maa'idah 5: 95), and he says: (but the game of the land has been prohibited so long as you are in the state of ihram) (al-Maa'idah 5: 96), so the legislation is the right of Allah alone, and whoever permitted to do what Allah has forbidden and vice versa, he already claimed some of the characteristics of Godliness, which is the right of Allah alone in the legislation according to Rashid Rida (Rashid Reza: 1990), and Al-Hakim narrated in al-Mustadruq from Abu al-Darda (may Allaah be pleased with him) that the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) said: "Whatever Allaah has permitted in His Book is halaal, whatever He has forbidden is haraam, and whatever He was silent about is pardoned, so accept the pardon of Allaah, for Allaah was not forgetful. Then he recited this verse: 'and your Lord is never forgetful' (Maryam 19:64)" (Al-Hakim: 1990), Therefore, there is no unlawful unless the evidence from religion indicates that it is unlawful, or the medicine or experiment indicate that it is harmful physically or spiritually, or what ethical people disgusted, so It is known from the above that permission and prohibition is the right of Allaah alone, and it is not authorised to anyone to forbid something if there is no evidence for prohibition.

TWO: ALL TAYYIB (GOOD) FOODS ARE LAWFUL

Allaah told that He allowed to His servants to benefit from all that the earth contains such as food and others with condition of being halal and good in itself and it is not harmful to the buddies or to the minds, he says: (They ask you what has been made lawful for them. Say, "All the good and pure things have been made lawful for you) until: (All the good and pure things have today been made lawful for you; the food of the people of the Book is lawful for you, and your food for them) (al-Maa'idah 5: 4-5), and he says: (Eat easefully of the lawful and pure things which Allah has provided you) (al-Maa'idah 5: 88), The commentators of the Salaf and al-Khalaf differed in the control of the description of the good mentioned in the verses, on the authority of al-Tabari: "Al-Tayyeb: What is pure, not unclean or forbidden" (Al-Tabari: 2001), and Al-Maturidi: Tayeb: "What pleases the soul of eating, because the soul does not enjoy the eating from all halal, but it is pleased for what is good and delicious" (Al-

Maturidi: 2005), and Fakhr al-Din al-Razi described Al-Tayyeb as the one which is delicious and desired (Al-Razi: 1999), and he said: "The referencing in the tasty and good foods is through the people of morale and beautiful ethics, because the Bedouin people eat all the animals" (Al-Razi: 1999), and Muhammad Abdo considered that a-tayyib is not related to the rights of others (Rashid Reza: 1990),

While Ibn Ashour sees that A-tayyib means: "What is pleasant by the souls With Rectal perception and proper of anomalies, and they are the souls that desire the full appropriate so it does not hurt her physically or spiritually" (Ibn Ashur: 1984). It appears to me after mentioning the words of scholars that: "The Halal and Tayyib is all that pleases and desires unless it is harmful, and is not disgusted, nor it is forbidden, nor unclean, nor it is derived from forbidden wealth, nor it is related to the right of others, and without excessive in it".

So it has been learned from the above that every food which is pleasant by Sharia is lawful for human, because the existence of human life is due to it, and without it the human life will not exist, some scientists said: "All that it is permitted by Allah, it is beneficial for the body and religion" (Ibn Katheer: 1999), And its benefit in the body is by strengthen it for the hardness and effort at work, and in religion is by strengthen it to engage in all acts of worship.

THREE: ALL WHAT IS PERMISSIBLE TO EAT FROM A LAND ANIMALS MUST BE SLAUGHTERED IN ACCORDANCE WITH THE ISLAMIC LAW. (SHARI'A)

Allaah told what He allowed to His servants from eatable animals, He says: (All grazing beasts of the flock are permitted to you) (al-Maa'idah 5: 1), the word bahimah means in the Arabic language: "All beasts with four lists of wild and water animals" (Ibnu Manzor: 1993), whereas the word an'am is a: "Name for camels, cattle and sheep especially" (Al-Tabari: 2001), and others included the wild animals such: "Gazelle, wild cows, and zebras" (Al-Tabari: 2001), and al-Maturidi considered that: "all eaten animals such sheep, wild animals, hunted animals and etc even if it is not mentioned" (Al-Maturidi: 2005), so we conclude that the word bahimatul- an'am in this verse denotes: "camels, cattle, sheep, including every wild animal or bird which feeds from the plant since there is no evidence from religion indicates that it is unlawful, except the animal of prey or predator", Ibn Qudamah said: "They asked Ahmed about the giraffe being eaten? He said: Yes. She is a creature like cattle, but her neck is longer than his neck, her body is nicer than his body, and taller than him, and her hands are longer than her legs" (Ibn Qudamah: 1968), and the proof of the permissibility to eat from a land animals must be slaughtered in accordance with the Islamic Law is the word of Allah: (except those which are recited to you hereinafter) (al-Maa'idah 5: 1), and the menanig is: "any animal or bird which has been slaughtered before his death is permissible to eat from it if it is among what Allah has permitted to His servant to eat from it" (Al-Tabari: 2001), the word tadhkiyyah in the Arabic dictionaries means: "slaughtering" (Ibnu Manzor: 1993), whereas in the religion means: "Slaughtering the animal or stabbing it by Cutting his throat or his esophagus" (Sayyid Sabiq: 1977), or: "Slaughtering or Slaying the domesticated animals or hunting the wild animals in accordance with the Islamic Law" (Altwajri: 2009).

Therefore, it is clear from the above that the slaughtering in accordance with the Islamic Law for the animal that is permissible to eat is by three ways:

- 1- Slaughtering:** Cutting the throat or the esophagus of the permitted animal for eating, and usually used in sheep, cattle and poultry and what is similar in size.
- 2- Slaying:** Stabbing in the throat and then cutting it up to the top of the chest, and usually used in for camels and what is similar in size.
- 3- Al 'Aqer:** Wounding an animal which cannot be slaughtered, whether it be a wild animal whose hunting is allowed or a domesticated animal that has gone wild.

Now, the requirements of animal slaughtering In accordance with the provisions of Islamic Sharia are as follow:

- 1-The Slaughterer must be sane, conscious, Man or Woman.
- 2- The Slaughterer must be a Muslim or a person of Ahl Al Kitab: a Jew or a Christian.
- 3- The slaughtering should be done by a sharp instrument, excluding the tooth, nail and other bones.

- 4- The hunting should be with a well-trained animals or with a good quality instrument.
- 5- The trained animal or any joined animals during the hunting, should not eat from the hunted animal according to Sahih Muslim that 'Adi b. Hatim reported: "I asked Allah's Messenger (May peace be upon him) saying: We are a people who hunt with these (trained) dogs, then (what should we do)? Thereupon he (the Holy Prophet) said: When you set of your trained dogs having recited the name of Allah, then eat what these (hounds) have caught for you, even if it (the game) is killed, provided (the hunting dog) has not eaten (any part of the game). If it has eaten (the game), then you don't eat it as I fear that it might have caught for its own self. And do not eat in case other dogs have joined your trained dogs" (Muslim: 2002).
- 6- The blood Must flow from the hunted animal otherwise it is considered as a dead animal.
- 7- The slaughtered animals must be from what Allah has permitted to eat from it.
- 8- The animals or birds must be slaughtered in accordance with the Islamic Law. (Shari'a)
- 9- The Slaughterer must mention the name of Allah when slaughtering (Bismillah), (Sayyid Sabiq: 1977), (Altwaijri: 2009).

FOUR: THE SACRIFICES WHICH ALLAH MADE LAWFUL FOR JEWS AND CHRISTIANS IN THEIR RESPECTIVE SCRIPTURES, IS LAWFUL FOR MUSLIMS

Allaah has permitted eating from the sacrifices of the people of the Book from Jews and the Christians, He said: (The food of the People of the Book is permitted to you) (al-Maa'idah 5: 5), Al-Bukhari in his Sahih according to Ibn Abbas said: "Their food: their sacrifices" (Al- Bukhari: 2002), and the scholar Ibn Shihab a-Zuhri commented: "There is nothing wrong with the sacrifice of the Arab Christians, and if you heard him [during the slaughtering] mentioning the name of anything or anyone other than Allah, then do not eat, and if you do not hear him, Allaah has permitted it to you and knew his kufr [Infidelity]" (Al- Bukhari: 2002), so this verse is evidence that the sacrifices of the people of the Book are valid for the Muslims, as long as the Jew or the Christian did not turn back from his religion, and slay in a legitimate manner, and Ibn Katheer has said about the sacrifices of the people of the Book: "This is a matter of consensus among the scholars that the sacrifices of the people of the Book are permissible for Muslims because they believe that it is forbidden to mention other name than Allah when slaughtering, and they do not mention on their sacrifices except the name of Allaah, even if they believe in Allaah what is not correct" (Ibn Katheer: 1999), and It has been narrated in Sahih Al-Bukhaari from Anas that a Jewish woman came to the Messenger of Allaah (peace and blessings of Allaah be upon him) with some poisoned mutton. The Messenger of Allaah (peace and blessings of Allaah be upon him) ate from it, then he asked her about that. She said, "I wanted to kill you." He said, "Allaah would not let you do that." They said, "Shall we kill her?" He said, "No." He said, I can still see the effect of that on the palate of the Messenger of Allaah (peace and blessings of Allaah be upon him) (Al- Bukhari: 2002).

Therefore, Allaah has permitted eating from the sacrifices of the people of the Book: "because they are based on a divine religion that forbids sins, and keeps away from impurity" (Ibn Ashur: 1984), But if the Muslim knows that the sacrifices of the people of the Book are slaughtered without following the legitimate way, such as suffocation, beatings or electric shocks, in this case, it is not permissible to eat from them at all, also the verse indicates that the sacrifices of non-people of the book such apostates, Magians, Hindus, Buddhists, atheists, idolaters and worshipers of idols are not permissible to eat them at all even if they are slaughtered in a legitimate manner because they do not have a divine religion.

So it is stipulated in the sacrifices of the people of the Book as follow:

1. They must mention the name of Allah when slaughtering (Bismillah).
2. They must Slaughter in a legitimate manner.
3. They must not apostate from their religion.

FIVE: PERMITTING ALL AQUATIC ANIMALS TO BE USED FOR FOOD WHETHER THEY ARE CAUGHT OR FOUND DEAD, AND IT DOES NOT MATTER WHO CAUGHT THEM

The Quran mentioned that it is permissible to eat all that lives in the sea, rivers and valleys, whether it is an animal or plant, a living or dead, Allah said: (The game of the sea and eating thereof are permitted to you) (al-Maa'idah 5: 96), Ibn 'Abbas said: "Sea game refers to what is taken from the sea while still alive, whilst sea food refers to what the sea throws ashore dead" (Al-Tabari: 2001), and the sea in the arabic language includes rivers and valleys because all are called seas as in the book of 'Lisan al- 'Arab' that a-Zajaj said: "Every river shall his water not be cut off, it is a sea" (Ibnu Manzor: 1993), That's why Rashid Rida said: "The sea means a lot of water where there is a fish and other aquatic animals that are caught, so it includes: rivers, wells, ponds and so on" (Rashid Reza: 1990), and Sayyiduna Abd Allah ibn Umar (Allah be pleased with him) narrates that the Messenger of Allah (Allah bless him & give him eternal peace) said: "Two types of dead meat and two types of blood have been made lawful for our consumption: The two dead meats are: fish and locust, and the two types of blood are: liver and spleen" (Ibn Hanbal: 2001), and Jabir (Allah be pleased with him) reported in Sahih Muslim that: "We then went to the coast of the sea, and there rose before us on the coast of the sea something like a big mound. We came near that and we found that it was a beast, called al-'Anbar (spermaceti whale). Abu 'Ubaida said. It is dead. He then said: No (but it does not matter), we have been sent by the Messenger of Allah (Peace be upon him) in the path of Allah and you are hard pressed (on account of the scarcity of food), so you eat that. We three hundred in number stayed there for a month, until we grew bulky. He (Jabir) said: I saw how we extracted pitcher after pitcher full of fat from the cavity of its eye, and sliced from it compact piece of meat equal to a bull or like a bull. Abu 'Ubaida called forth thirteen men from us and he made them sit in the cavity of its eye, and he took hold of one of the ribs of its chest and made it stand and then saddled the biggest of the camels we had with us and it passed under it (the arched rib), and we provided ourselves with pieces of boiled meat (especially for use in our journey). When we came back to Medina, we went to Allah's Messenger (Peace be upon him) and made a mention of that to him, whereupon he said: That was a provision which Allah had brought forth for you. Is there any piece of meat (left) with you, so that you give to us? He (Jabir) said: We sent to Allah's Messenger (Peace be upon him) some of that (a piece of meat) and he ate it" (Muslim: 2002), so we conclude that all what the sea throws ashore dead is lawful, regardless of who hunts it, as Imam Malik said: "There is nothing wrong with eating whales caught by a Magian (Majusi), because the Messenger of Allah, may Allah bless him and grant him peace, said, "In the sea's water is purity, and that which is dead in it is halal (Malik: 2004), then he said: "If he eats the dead fish, it does not matter who caught it" (Malik: 2004).

Thus, we conclude from this legitimate control that:

1. All the water game are lawful for eating.
2. All the water's dead animals are lawful for eating.
3. It is not required a legitimate method in the water game.
- 4 - It is permissible to eat what is caught by the non-people of book such the Magians and outers.

SIX: ALL MALICIOUS FOODS ARE UNLAWFUL

In regards with the malicious foods, the Quran has mostly commented on most of them when he said: (Forbidden to you are carrion, blood, the flesh of swine, the animal slaughtered in any name other than Allah's, the animal which has either been strangled, killed by blows, has died of a fall, by goring or that devoured by a beast of prey - unless it be that which you yourselves might have slaughtered while it was still alive and that which was slaughtered at the altars) (al-Maa'idah 5: 3), and the scholars unanimously agreed that it is not permissible to eat the impure food because it harms the body, based on what Allah said: (and forbids them what is evil) (Al-A'raaf 7: 157), and Evil (Khabith) means: "What is harmful, or causes bad effect, or is impure not accepted by the wise people, like uncleanness" (Ibn Ashur: 1984), and the uncleanness food such: "Insects, worms, beetle, cockroach, Mouse, Geckos,

Chameleons, Rats, Scorpions and Snakes” (Ibn Qudamah: 1968), and it derives from this legitimate control:

1- All harmful food are not allowed to be eaten even if it is permitted by the Shari'a: such eating fish that lives in a contaminated water, so the origin of eating fish generally is the permissibility as we have known earlier, but it is forbidden to benefit from it if it comes from a poisoned water which can affect the body badly, and Ibn ‘Abbas (Allah be pleased with them) reported in Sunan ibn Majah that Allah's Messenger (Peace be upon him) said: “Do not cause harm or return harm” (Ibn Majah: 2002), thus we conclude on this point that forbidding the lawful things is because of containing a harmful products, and when it is cleaned from the harmful products it returns to its origin which is the permissibility of use.

2- If the unlawful food mix up with the lawful food it is forbidden to use it: such cooking the Halal meat with the lard (fat of pig) or wine, in this case the Halal meat becomes unlawful, even if it has been mixed up with a very few quantity of lard or wine, Abu Hurairah (Allah be pleased with them) reported in Sunan abu daud that Allah's Messenger (Peace be upon him) said: “When a mouse falls into clarified butter, if it is sold, throw the mouse and what is around it away, but if it is in a liquid state, do not go near it” (Abu Dawud: 1990).

3- It is not permissible to waste food: In regards to forbid to eat halal food with excessiveness it is clear on Allah’s word: (Believers! Do not hold as unlawful the good things which Allah has made lawful to you, and do not exceed the bounds of right. Allah does not love those who transgress the bounds of right.) (Al-Maa'idah 5: 87), and the meaning: “Do not exaggerate in dealing with halal, and do not transgress the limits by excessively indulging in the permissible matters, only use of it what satisfies your need” (Ibn Katheer: 1999), therefor Islam censured in the excessiveness in eating, It has been reported In Sahih Al- Bukhari that Ibn Umar (Allah be pleased with them) said that Allah's Messenger (Peace be upon him) said: "A believer eats in one intestine (is satisfied with a little food), and a kafir (unbeliever) or a hypocrite eats in seven intestines (eats too much)” (Al- Bukhari: 2002), the Scholar Al- Halaimi said: “Eating too much make the body heavy and leads him to sleep, and prevents him from worship, but you may eat as much as your hunger, and the purpose of eating is to strengthen the body in order to worship Allah” (Al-Bayhaqi: 2003), and it better for the human to have one-third for his food, one-third for his drink, and one-third for himself, so Miqdam bin Ma'dikarib (Allah be pleased with him) reported that Allah's Messenger (Peace be upon him) said: “The human does not fill any container that is worse than his stomach. It is sufficient for the son of Adam to eat what will support his back. If this is not possible, then a third for food, a third for drink, and third for his breath”(Tirmidhi: 1975).

So it has been learned from the above that:

- 1- Every food which is unpleasant by Sharia is unlawful for human, because it caused a bad effect in the human bodies, some scientists said: “All that it is not permitted by Allah, it is harmful for the body and religion” (Ibn Katheer: 1999), and its harms the body by making it lazy at work, and lazy in performing all acts of worship.
- 2- All harmful food are not allowed to be eaten even if it is permitted by the Shari'a.
- 3- If the unlawful food mix up with the lawful food it is forbidden to use it.
- 4- It is not permissible to waste food.

SEVEN: ALL THE DEAD LAND ANIMALS ARE UNLAWFUL EXCEPT THE DEAD LOCUSTS

Allah forbade to his servants to eat the dead of animals and birds, and has excluded from that the dead locust, the detail in this matter is as below:

1- The dead of animals and birds: The scholars unanimously agreed on the prohibition of eating the dead of animals and birds, even though it is one of the sex of what Allaah has permitted, as long as it is

not slaughtered in accordance with the Islamic Law according to the evidence of Allah Almighty in His book: (Forbidden to you are carrion, ...unless it be that which you yourselves might have slaughtered while it was still alive) (Al-Maa'idah 5: 3), the word 'maitah' in the religion signifies : "The domesticated and wild animal or bird which is allowed to eat, and her soul separated her without slaughtering" (Al-Tabari: 2001), and Allah said in detail about carrion that are: (The animal which has either been strangled, killed by blows, has died of a fall, by goring or that devoured by a beast of prey) (Al-Maa'idah 5: 3). Thus, any animal that was already dead when found (maitah), regardless of the cause of death, is unlawful for consumption. A verse details some categories of dead animals:

- 1- An animal strangled, by rope or by inserting her head in a place where she cannot get rid of it, then she suffocates until she dies (Al-Tabari: 2001); also an animal strangled is killed by human by strangulation, typically with an iron collar or a length of wire or cord, Imam Qatāda ibn Di'āma reported that: "The ignorant people used to suffocate the animal till its death, than they eat it" (Al-Tabari: 2001).
- 2- An animal that dies stunned by a blunt object until she dies (Al-Tabari: 2001); Imam Qatāda ibn Di'āma reported that: "The ignorant people used to beat the animal with sticks till its death, than they eat it" (Al-Tabari: 2001).
- 3- An animal that dies as a result of a fall from high place (Ibn Katheer: 1999); Imam Qatāda ibn Di'āma reported that: "The ignorant people used to eat the animal which dies as a result of fall down in the hole" (Al-Tabari: 2001).
- 4- An animal that dies after being gored by horns (Al-Tabari: 2001); Imam Qatāda ibn Di'āma reported that: "The ignorant people used to eat the dead animal after being gored by horns" (Al-Tabari: 2001).
- 5- An animal whose body has been partially devoured by predator animal, such lion, Leopard, tiger, wolf, dog and dies as result of the attack (Ibn Katheer: 1999); Imam Qatāda ibn Di'āma reported that: "The ignorant people used to eat the dead animal after being attacked by a prey animal" (Ibn Katheer: 1999). Thus, all these animals that have been died without legitimate slaughtering are unlawful even if the predator has attacked it by the throat or any other part in its body and caused, as a result, the release of its blood.

1- The dead of locust: the locusts were mentioned in the Qur'an as a soldier of God sent to the disobedient of his slaves, He said: (Then We afflicted them with a great flood and locusts, and the lice, and the frogs, and the blood. All these were distinct signs and yet they remained haughty. They were a wicked people) (Al-A'raaf 7: 133), and were also mentioned when people were described on the day of judgement that they came out from their graves as though they were scattered locusts in every direction, Allah said: (they shall go forth from their graves, with down-cast eyes as though they were scattered locusts) (Al-Qamar 54: 7), and the evidence of permissibility of eating the locusts is according to Sunan Ibn Majah that Abdullah Bin Umar (Allah be pleased with them) reported that Allah's Messenger (Peace be upon him) said : "Two types of dead meat and two types of blood have been made lawful for our consumption: The two dead meats are: fish and locust, and the two types of blood are: liver and spleen" (Ibn Hanbal: 2001), also in Sahih Al-Bukhari, Abi Yafour Narrated that Ibn Abi Aufa (Allah be pleased with them) reported that Allah's Messenger (Peace be upon him) said: "We participated with the Prophet in six or seven Ghazawat, and we used to eat locusts with him" (Al-Bukhari: 2002). Both hadeeths are report and endorsement of the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allaah be upon him) that it is permissible to use the dead of locusts.

Thus, it has been learned from the above that:

- 1 - Every eatable animal died without a legitimate slaughtering is forbidden for eating, even if the blood released from its body.
2. Permission to eat the dead of locusts.

EIGHT: ALL WHAT IS FORBIDDEN TO EAT FROM A LAND ANIMALS IS NOT ALLOWED EVEN IF THEY ARE SLAUGHTERED IN ACCORDANCE WITH THE ISLAMIC LAW. (SHARI'A)

The forbidden eatable animals even if they are slaughtered in accordance with the Islamic Law are:

1- What is forbidden by Islamic Law (Shari'a):

- **Domesticated Ass and Mules:** Most of scholars tend to forbid eating donkeys and mules with evidence of that they were permissible at the beginning of Islam and then the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allaah be upon him) forbade them on the day of Khaibar, Jabir (Allah be pleased with him) reported in Sahih Bukhari that: "On the day of Khaibar, Allah's Apostle forbade the eating of donkey meat and allowed the eating of horse meat" (Al- Bukhari: 2002), and in narration of Muslim: "Jabir b. 'Abdullah reported that Allah's Messenger (Peace be upon him) prohibited eating of the flesh of domestic asses on the Day of Khaibar, and permitted the cooking of the flesh of horses" (Muslim: 2002), and the Asses are: "those that they are familiar with houses and they have owners, and they are like domesticated opposite of wild (Ibnu Manzor: 1993), and they are inclusive of mules, donkeys and horses, Jabir (Allah be pleased with him) reported in Sunan Abu Dawood that: "On the day of Khaibar we slaughtered horses, mules, and asses. The Messenger of Allah (Peace be upon him) forbade us (to eat) mules and asses, but he did not forbid horse-flesh" (Abu Dawud: 1990), and it may be forbidden because it have been created for riding and adornment and not for eating according to Allah's word: (And He created horses and mules and asses for you to ride, and also for your adornment. And He creates many things (for you) that you do not even know about) (Al-Nahl 16: 8), Ibn Qudamah said: The majority of the scholars see the prohibition of eating Asses, and the Mule is forbidden for those who forbade the Ass, because the Mule was given birth from the Ass and the horse" (Ibn Qudamah: 1968).

- **Jallalah:** The scholars have stated that it is prohibited to eat Jallalah from animals and birds, and Jallalah signifies: "The animals that eat excrements, and trace impurities, and Jillah means droppings, and camel Jallalah is that eats excrements" (Ibn Manzor: 1993), and Sayyiduna Abd Allah ibn Umar (Allah be pleased with them) narrates that: "The Prophet (Peace be upon him) prohibited eating the Jallalah and milking it" (Tirmidhi: 1975), and Imam Nasa'i reported that: "on the Day of Khaibar, the Messenger of Allah forbade the flesh of domesticated donkeys and of al-Jallalah (animals that eat dung), and (he forbade) riding them and eating their meat" (Al-Nasā'i: 1986), so it is understood from this two Hadiths that three things are forbidden from Jallalah which are: Eating its meat, drinking its milk and riding it, and in addition: eating its egg if it gives eggs, we understood also that the reason of prohibiting al- Jallalah because it eats the waste or flesh, and if it stops eating the waste for a while, it becomes lawful, Therefore, the scholars see that the prohibition of the Jallalah is related to the animal which consumes most of its food from impurity, whereas if the majority of its food is from the purity, so it is not included in the prohibition, al-Khattabi said: "Al- Jallalah is the camel that eats Jillah which is the excrements, it is forbidden to eat it and milk it if the majority of its food is from the impurity which causes the pollution of its body, but if the majority of its food is from the purity, and eats some excrements, it is not considered as Jallalah Such as chicken and other animals that may have received something from excrements, and most of its food is from purity, so it is not forbidden to eat it" (Al-Khattabi: 1932), Ibn Taymiyyah (may Allaah have mercy on him) has searched about the question of how to purify the Jallalah in order to make it lawful by saying: "The prophet (Peace and blessings of Allaah be upon him) forbade to eat Jallalah or milk it, and if the Jallalah animal is quarantine and was fed clean normal diet is halal by majority of Muslims" (Ibn Taymiyyah: 2005), and Ibn Qudama mentioned the period of confinement the Jallalah until it is purified from impurity, He said: "The chicken Jallalah shall be quarantined for three days, and the camels Jallalah, the cows Jallalah and what is similar in its size shall be quarantined for forty days" (Ibn Qudamah: 1968).

- **The domesticated Pork or wild:** The scholars unanimously agreed on the prohibition of the meat of Pork including any part of its body, Allah said: (Forbidden to you are carrion, blood, the flesh of

swine) (Al-Maaida 7: 3), Imam Tabari said: “As for pork, its appearance is like its interior, and its interior is like its appearance, all is forbidden, nothing was specified from it” (Al-Tabari: 2001); and Ibn Kathir said: “The flesh includes all its parts even the fat” (Ibn Katheer: 1999), and there is no difference between the domesticated Pork and wild Pork for the majority of scholars, So al-Mawardi believes that the prohibition of pork: “including the flesh and what mix with it such fat and others, and this is the point of view of the majority of scholars, and there is no difference between the domestic Pork and the wild Pork” (Al-Mawardi: 1986).

- The slaughtered animal for purposes of worship the other Gods rather than Allah: according to: (the animal slaughtered in any name other than Allah`s) (Al-Maaida 7: 3), and the meaning: “What is slaughtered or slayed by pronouncing the name of anyone or anything other than God, and dedicating it as an offering to either a holy personage, god or goddess by sacrifices” (Rashid Reza: 1990), Abu Ja’far said: “What is sacrificed to the goddess and idols by pronouncing the name of anyone other than Allah” (Al-Tabari: 2001).

Therefore, we have learnt from the above that the forbidden foods are four categories:

1. Domesticated Ass and Mules.
2. Jallalah.
3. Domesticated Pork or wild including all parts of its body.
4. The eatable animals or birds which were slaughtered for purposes of worship the other Gods rather than Allah.

2. What is ordered or warned to be killed from animals by Islamic Law (Shari'a):

The Scholars unanimously agreed on the prohibition of eating the animals that were ordered to be killed by Islamic Law or were warned to be killed by Islamic Law, Narrated 'Aisha (Allah be pleased with them) that: “The Prophet said, "Five kinds of animals are mischief-doers (harmful) and can be killed even in the Sanctuary: They are the rat, the scorpion, the kite, the crow and the rabid dog"(Al- Bukhari: 2002), in another narration of Imam Muslim: “Snake” instead of: “scorpion” (Muslim: 2002), in addition there is an order for killing the gecko because is harmful, ‘Amir b. Sa’d, narrated that: “The Messenger of Allah (May peace be upon him) commanded the killing of geckos, and he called them little noxious creatures” (Muslim: 2002), and: “noxious” signifies: “They go out to the people and attack them, so they cannot protect themselves from them, and its aggression is more greater than the aggression of the predators” (Ibn Taymiyyah: 2005), and these noxious creatures mentioned here are mostly amongst poisonous carriers, and eating them it is same as drinking a poison to kill yourself, that's why the Sharia considered that who drinks a poison intentionally to kill himself is in the hell fire forever, Al-Bukhari in his Sahih according to Abu Huraira narrated that: “The Prophet said, "Whoever purposely throws himself from a mountain and kills himself, will be in the (Hell) Fire falling down into it and abiding therein perpetually forever; and whoever drinks poison and kills himself with it, he will be carrying his poison in his hand and drinking it in the (Hell) Fire wherein he will abide eternally forever; and whoever kills himself with an iron weapon, will be carrying that weapon in his hand and stabbing his abdomen with it in the (Hell) Fire wherein he will abide eternally forever” (Al- Bukhari: 2002), So any animal or insect or plant has been proven that carries the poison or damage, it is permissible to destroy it according to what were mentioned in the previous hadeeths, and the rule of the scholars said: “Any harmful creature, can be killed in accordance with Islamic law” (Al ‘Aini: 2002), and in regards what is forbidden to be killed in accordance with Islamic law, It was narrated that Ibn ‘Abbas said:

“The Messenger of Allah (Peace be upon him) forbade killing four kinds of animals: Ants, bees, hoopoes and shrikes” (Ibn Hanbal: 2001), in another narration of Ibn Majah: “frogs” instead of: “Ants” (Ibn Majah: 2002), and Imam Muslim reported in his Sahih, book of greetings, chapter of prohibition of killing the cat, that Abu Huraira reported Allah's Messenger (Peace be upon him) as saying: A woman was punished because of a cat. She had neither provided her with food nor drink, nor set her free so that she might eat the insects of the earth (Muslim: 2002).

We conclude from the above that the animals that were ordered to be killed by Islamic Law are: the rat, the scorpion, the kite, the crow, the rabid dog, the snake and the Geckos, and in regards with the animals that were warned to be killed by Islamic Law are: Ants, bees, hoopoes, shrikes, frogs and cats, and any animal shares with these animals which were ordered to be killed and vice versa in the reason, the prohibition will follow it, because the ruling revolves with its reason whether existing or not as mentioned by the scholars of Fiqh and usul.

3. Prohibition of eating every predator that possesses canine teeth: It has been

Mentioned by the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allaah be upon him) in more than one hadeeth that it is forbidden to eat every predator that possesses canine teeth, Al-Bukhari reported that Abu Tha'laba said: "The prophet (peace and blessings of Allaah be upon him) prohibited the eating of every fanged beast of prey" (Al-Bukhari: 2002), and in another narration by Imam Muslim that: Abu Huraira reported that the Allah's Messenger (Peace be upon him) said: "The eating of all fanged beasts of prey is unlawful" (Muslim: 2002), and (every fanged beast of prey) means: "Is the one that attacks the thing by using its fangs and then prey it" (Ibn Qudamah: 1968), Ibn Qudaamah said: "This is an explicit statement specifies the general verses, which includes the lion, the tiger, the leopard, the wolf, the dog and the pig, it was Narrated by al-Shaabi, that he was asked about a man who treats himself with the dog's flesh. He answered: May Allah do not cure him" (Ibn Qudamah: 1968).

4. Prohibition of eating every bird that possesses talons: It has been Mentioned by

The Prophet (peace and blessings of Allaah be upon him) in more than one hadeeth that it is forbidden to eat every bird that possesses talons, Ibn 'Abbas reported that: "Allah's Messenger (Peace be upon him) prohibited the eating of all fanged beasts of prey, and all the birds having talons" (Muslim: 2002), and (all the birds having talons) means: "Is the one that attaches the thing by using its talons and then hunts it" (Ibn Qudamah: 1968). Ibn Qudaamah said: "It includes every bird that possesses talons and hunts with it such as the eagle, the falcon, the saker, the accipiter, the glede, the owl, and so on" (Ibn Qudamah: 1968).

NINE: THE IMPERMISSIBILITY OF DRINKING THE UNCLEAR LIQUIDS

The lawful drinks are all drinks which are good, clean and beneficial, such as: the water, the oil, the honey, the ginger, the vinegar, the coffee, the tea, the juice, the mint and all that is extracted from animals that are permitted to eat like the milk, the butter, the cheese, the urine and other drinks that Allah created for the benefit of humans, and ordered them to drink without any extravagance.

Whereas the unlawful drinks are all malicious drink, unclean, harmful, and poisoned, such the wine and all intoxicants, the venom, and all that is extracted from animals that are not permitted to eat like the milk, the butter, the cheese, the urine and others.

So, we will focus here on the mentioned forbidden drinks in Surat Al-Maa'idah, which are two types:

1- The spilled blood except the liver and the spleen: according to: (Forbidden to you are carrion, blood) (Al-Maaida 5: 3), and the blood here means the spilled blood according to another verse which says: (outpoured blood) (Al-An'aam 6: 145), and the outpoured blood signifies: "the blood which has flowed as a result of either injuring or slaughtering an animal even if it is dried after that" (Rashid Reza: 1990), whereas the liver and the spleen are excluded according to the narration of Sayyiduna Abd Allah ibn Umar (May Allah be pleased with them) that the Messenger of Allah (peace and blessings of Allaah be upon him) said: "Two types of dead meat and two types of blood have been made lawful for our consumption: The two dead meats are: fish and locust, and the two types of blood are: liver and spleen" (Ibn Hanbal: 2001).

2- The wine and every drink that produces intoxication: according to: (Believers! Intoxicants, games of chance, idolatrous sacrifices at altars, and divining arrows are all abominations, the handiwork of Satan. So turn wholly away from it that you may attain to true success) (Al-Maaida 5: 90), and Al-Khamr (alcohol) in the Arabic language signifies: "What covers the mind, which is the intoxicant of the

drink” (Ibnu Manzor: 1993), and Allah has clarified the reason behind forbidding the intoxicant which is because of creating the enmity and hatred between people, and turn them away from worshipping Allah, as He said: (By intoxicants and games of chance Satan only desires to create enmity and hatred between you, and to turn you away from the remembrance of Allah and from Prayer. Will you, then, desist?) (Al-Maaida 5: 91), and for your information, the wine is not limited to grape juice only, otherwise all that makes you drunk is wine, Sayyidatuna Aisha (May Allah be pleased with her) Narrated that The Prophet (peace and blessings of Allaah be upon him) said, "All drinks that produce intoxication are forbidden" (Al- Bukhari: 2002), and in another narration by Imam Muslim that: Ibn 'Umar (May Allah be pleased with them) reported that the Allah's Messenger (Peace be upon him) said: “Every intoxicant is Khamr and every intoxicant is forbidden. He who drinks wine in this world and dies while he is addicted to it, not having repented, will not be given a drink in the Hereafter” (Muslim: 2002), and also what is narrated Ibn Umar (May Allah be pleased with them) that he said: I heard 'Umar (May Allah be pleased with him) while he was on the pulpit of the Prophet saying, "Now then O people! The revelation about the prohibition of alcoholic drinks was revealed; and alcoholic drinks are extracted from five things: Grapes, dates, honey, wheat and barley. And the alcoholic drink is that which confuses and stupefies the mind" (Al- Bukhari: 2002).

Thus, we conclude from this legitimate ruling as follow:

- 1- The prohibition of outpoured blood except the liver and the spleen.
- 2- All drinks that produce intoxication are forbidden.

TEN: PERMITTING THE FORBIDDEN FOODS AND DRINKS IN CONDITIONS OF NECESSITY

We conclude these legitimate controls with what was permitted by Allah to his servants to feed themselves from the above-mentioned forbidden foods when absolutely necessary as he said: (Forbidden to you are carrion, blood, the flesh of swine, the animal slaughtered in any name other than Allah`s, the animal which has either been strangled, killed by blows, has died of a fall, by goring or that devoured by a beast of prey - unless it be that which you yourselves might have slaughtered while it was still alive and that which was slaughtered at the altars –till His saying- As for he who is driven by hunger, without being wilfully inclined to sin, surely Allah is All-Forgiving, All-Compassionate.) (al-Maa'idah 5: 3), and the necessity in the Arabic language means: “The need for the thing, and the man with necessity means: he is in need, and he was forced to do something means compelled to it” (Ibnu Manzor: 1993), whereas in the religion means: “Fear of harm or loss of the soul or loss of some parts of the body when quitting the eating” (Al-Jassas: 1994). Thus the meaning of the verse will be: “The one who is constrained to eat what has been mentioned, then he ate from it because was driven by hunger, and he did not find permitted food, without being desired the prohibited food and without being wilfully inclined to sin, surely Allah is All-Forgiving, All-Compassionate” (Rashid Reza: 1990), The Sunnah took the full responsibility for those who left the forbidden foods when necessary and guided themselves automatically to the destruction, according to the narration of Sayyiduna Abd Allah ibn Umar (May Allah be pleased with them) that the Messenger of Allah (peace and blessings of Allaah be upon him) said: “The one who did not accept the God's Rukhsah (allowance) he will be a guilty of committing the sin like a mountains of Arafat” (Ibn Hanbal: 2001), This is why the fuqaha' said: “It may be obligatory to eat the dead animals in some times, if he fears to die and he doesn't find what is permitted to eat, and it may be desirable or lawful depending on the circumstances” (Ibn Katheer: 1999). Thus, we conclude from this legitimate ruling that Allah has permitted to his servants to eat what is forbidden when necessary without being desired it and without being wilfully inclined to sin, and that the one who rejects this Rukhsah (allowance) and presenting himself to perdition he is already committed a major sin.

Conclusion

Last but not least, the main findings of this research are as follows:

1. Permitting to eat all aquatic animals whether they are caught or found dead, unless they are hazardous to life or health. As the Qur'an states, (The game of the sea and eating thereof are permitted to you) (al-Maa'idah 5: 96).
2. Permitting to eat all land animals if they are not hazardous to life or health except:
 - What was not slaughtered in accordance with the Islamic law.
 - The dead animals.
 - The domesticated swine or wild including all parts of its body.
 - The domesticated Ass and Mules.
 - The Jallalah until it is purified from impurity.
 - What is ordered to be killed from animals by Islamic Law (Shari'a).
 - What is warned to be killed from animals by Islamic Law (Shari'a)
 - Every predator that possesses canine teeth.
 - Every bird that possesses talons.
 - What was slaughtered for purposes of worship the other Gods rather than Allah. As the Qur'an states, (Forbidden to you are carrion, blood, the flesh of swine, the animal slaughtered in any name other than Allah's, the animal which has either been strangled, killed by blows, has died of a fall, by goring or that devoured by a beast of prey - unless it be that which you yourselves might have slaughtered while it was still alive and that which was slaughtered at the altars) (al-Maa'idah 5: 3).
3. Permitting to eat all forbidden foods and drinks in conditions of necessity. As the Qur'an states, (As for he who is driven by hunger, without being wilfully inclined to sin, surely Allah is all-Forgiving, All-Compassionate.) (al-Maa'idah 5: 3).
4. Allah has forbidden to eat all harmful food even if it is permitted by the Shari'a, and if the unlawful food mix up with the lawful food it is forbidden to use it, and it is not permissible to waste food. As the Qur'an states, (Believers! Do not hold as unlawful the good things which Allah has made lawful to you, and do not exceed the bounds of right. Allah does not love those who transgress the bounds of right.) (Al-Maa'idah 5: 87).
5. Permitting to consume all drinks except: the outpoured blood and the wine inclusive drinks that produce intoxication. As the Qur'an states, (Forbidden to you are carrion, blood) (al-Maa'idah 5: 3), also: (Believers! Intoxicants, games of chance, idolatrous sacrifices at altars, and divining arrows are all abominations, the handiwork of Satan. So turn wholly away from it that you may attain to true success) (Al-Maaida 5: 90).
6. The main legitimate controls on halal food based on Surat Al-Ma'idah are:
 - The Impermissibility of forbidding the lawful foods and permitting the unlawful foods.
 - All tayyib (good) foods are lawful.
 - All what is permissible to eat from a land animals must be slaughtered in accordance with the Islamic Law. (Shari'a).
 - The sacrifices which Allah made lawful for Jews and Christians in their respective scriptures, is lawful for Muslims.
 - Permitting all aquatic animals to be used for food whether they are caught or found dead, and it does not matter who caught them.
 - All malicious foods are unlawful.

- All the dead land animals are unlawful except the dead locusts.
- All what is forbidden to eat from a land animals is not allowed even if they are slaughtered in accordance with the Islamic Law. (Shari'a).
- The Impermissibility of drinking the unclean liquids.
- Permitting the forbidden foods and drinks in Conditions of Necessity.

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